

Monitoring of Pesticide Residues in Lebanese Table Grapes and Potential Health Risks Associated with Exposure to Detected Pesticides

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Abstract: The purpose of the present surveillance is to investigate the levels of pesticide residues in fresh table grapes from Lebanon's major agricultural regions. A total of 588 fresh grapes samples were collected by sampling campaign. The average levels of extraction recovery performed using QUECHERS method ranged between 76 and 98% with a relative standard deviation (RSD) of less than 20%. This demonstrates compliance with European regulations. Out of the 128 formulations studied, 44 pesticides were detected (54.5% fungicides, 40.9% insecticides and, 4.6% herbicides and acaricides). The most frequently detected residues in grapes were cyprodinil, azoxystrobin, thiophanate-methyl, difenoconazole, cypermethrin, and carbendazim. Most of the detected pesticide residues belong to Triazole, Benzimidazole, Strobilurin, and Anilinopyrimidine chemical groups. The results also revealed a cocktail of pesticide residues containing up to 7 molecules in the same sample. Pesticide residues above Maximum Residue Level (MRL) were detected in 18.45% of the samples, as thiophanate-methyl, difenoconazole, cypermethrin, acetamiprid, and tetraconazole and 81.54% contained residues below the MRL. The sampling production showed the presence of pesticide residues; 74.7% in Beqaa Valley, 25% in North Lebanon, and 0.37% in South Lebanon. Notably, none of the Organochlorine pesticides is found in the Lebanese table grapes samples. While assessing the risk exposure of humans to pesticide residues, the study shows that; 16 are known probable carcinogens, 18 are genotoxic, 17 are suspected endocrine disruptors, 36 are developmental or reproductive toxins, and 14 are neurotoxins. However, following the recommended application of WHO guidelines, pesticide residues detected above MRL are unlikely to present significant health concerns to the Lebanese populations as the short (HI) and long-term (cHI) risk index were both below 100%. Based on the results; the Lebanese Ministry of Agriculture has succeeded in banning 16 pesticides to reduce the potential health risk to consumers, where unfortunately three of these pesticides are still authorized in Europe. Regular monitoring of pesticide residues and sensitization of farmers to good agricultural practices, particularly the necessity to adhere to pre-harvest intervals, are highly recommended.

Keywords: Table Grapes; Pesticide Residues; Monitoring Programs; Food safety; Dietary exposure; Health risk assessment; QuEChERS.

1. Introduction

Grapes (*Vitis vinifera* L.) are one of Lebanon's most nutritionally significant crops. It is a widely consumed and grown fruit around the world, where it is consumed as fresh table grapes and processed into different products such as juices, wine, and raisins (Kandyli, 2021). Since the late 4th millennium B.C., about 6 thousand years ago, Lebanon was one of the first countries worldwide that had been growing grapes for both table grapes and wine, where Phoenicians used to export the grapes and wine to Europe from the Mediterranean countries (McGovern, Fleming and Katz, 2005). According to FAO stats 2020 (Faostat, 2021), viticulture occupies 7193 hectares of the Lebanese total agricultural areas (258,000 hectares), producing about 62,955 tons of grapes annually. Of the total vineyard areas in Lebanon (Rahhal, 2018), 70% are devoted to table grapes, located in Beqaa valley, at an altitude of 1000 m, comprising 69% of the vineyard area (Antoun, 2014). Its location between the East and West Mount Lebanon mountain chains shields the grapes from high humidity and hot temperatures (Abu Ghyda and Fahs, 2007).

Grapes are considered a healthful foodstuff having a positive impact on human health. It contains many bioactive components like resveratrol, quercetin, anthocyanin, vitamins, and catechins. These components are as beneficial as antimicrobial, antioxidant (Pezzuto, 2008), anti-cancer (Kuršvietienė et al., 2016; C. K. Singh et al., 2016), anti-inflammatory (Imran et al., 2017), and cardiovascular cure (Dohadwala and Vita, 2009; Rahbar, Mahmoudabadi and Islam, 2015). Grapevines, on the other hand, can be affected by a variety of diseases during the growth phase. The most frequent diseases caused by fungi are downy mildew (*Plasmopara viticola*), grey mildew (*Botrytis cinerea*), and powdery mildew (*Uncinula necator*) (González-Rodríguez, 2009). Pesticides have been applied to grapevines for pest management against these plant and animal parasites, as well as to increase production yield (Xiao et al., 2020). However, their presence in crops and broad-spectrum biocide activity is a major worldwide public health and environmental concern (Pimentel, 2005). As a result, toxic substances in grapes should not exceed specified standard limits.

One of the greatest challenges confronting public health is improving knowledge about the dietary risk of chemical contaminants. Pesticides can have a range of possible health impacts, both short-term and long-term, depending on the type of pesticide, the dose and duration of exposure, and individual susceptibility. Short-term effects may include symptoms like nausea and headache, while long-term effects may include chronic effects like cancer, neurotoxicity, cytogenetic damage, endocrine disturbance, and infertility (Cecchi et al., 2012; Alavanja, Ross and Bonner, 2013). It is important to consider these potential health risks when monitoring pesticide residues in food products, such as table grapes, to ensure the safety of consumers. Due to their high food intake/body weight ratio and the immaturity of their defense systems against chemical stresses, babies and young children under the age of three are particularly sensitive to several chemicals (Nougadère et al., 2020). Thus, many organizations (*Codex Alimentarius Commission*, 2022; *EU Pesticides Database*, 2022; *US-EPA Regulations*, 2022) monitor pesticide application on food commodities by establishing legal limits as maximum residual limits (MRLs) to ensure human's safety. Food containing pesticide residues exceeding MRL levels is not necessarily unsafe, since MRL is a product limit, not a safety limit (European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), Carrasco Cabrera and Medina Pastor, 2021). A post-marketing assessment of food intake and pesticide residue risk is also carried out by researchers and EFSA (EFSA, 2022).

Pesticide use is not strictly regulated in Lebanon. There is no authorization system to manage the purchase and usage of pesticides by farmers (Nasreddine et al., 2016). The lack of adequate knowledge of the farmers regarding the

safe and judicious use of pesticides is the main reason for the preened contaminants, they tend to apply the pesticides too close to harvest without taking into consideration the Preharvest interval (PHI) (Khan, Parveen and Ahmed, 2007; Bempah and Donkor, 2011). Furthermore, the Ministry of Agriculture (MoA) in Lebanon is striving to monitor and reduce pesticides usage by educating farmers through technical agricultural schools and offering comprehensive training programs such as Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) and Integrated Pest Management (IPM) (Fahed and Hayar, 2021).

Many analytical methods have been developed to determine the pesticide residues in table grapes, they were known to be time-consuming and expensive, while (Anastassiades *et al.*, 2003) recently developed a quick, easy, cheap, and effective (QuEChERS) method for determining pesticide concentration. A reliable and sensitive analytical method was used to quantify the molecules at low concentrations was validated by our team on vine leaves (Hayar, Zeitoun and Maestroni, 2021). It is a highly selective and sensitive method to determine the pesticide, offering simultaneous quantitation and confirmation of many pesticides used in Lebanon with excellent separation with a wide range of sensitive and selective detectors. The analyses were determined by instrumental techniques that separate analytes such as gas chromatography (GC) and/or liquid chromatography (LC) coupled to mass spectrometry.

This study presents the results of a pesticide monitoring assessment conducted on table grape samples collected in Lebanon in 2012. The objective of this study was to: (1) analyze 588 table grape samples collected in three different districts of Lebanon to determine pesticide exposure levels, (2) conduct a quantitative dietary risk assessment, and (3) establish a database that could be used to assess the levels of multi-class pesticide residues in table grapes in Lebanon to ensure regulatory compliance.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

On the eastern Mediterranean coastlines, Lebanon is located between 35° and 36°40' east longitude and 33° and 34°40' north latitude. The average annual rainfall range between 700-1000 mm.year⁻¹ and the relative humidity is 69.3%. Samples were collected from three major viticulture regions in Lebanon. Zahle and Baalbeck-Hermel in the Beqaa Valley, North Lebanon (Akkar Valley), and South Lebanon. The locations chosen were those with higher pesticide use and large agricultural production of grapes, sites are shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Grape cultivation in Lebanon (Frem *et al.*, 2021).

2.2. Sample Collection and Preparation

For the evaluation of pesticide residues, 588 samples were collected during the harvesting period from July for early varieties until the first week of November for late-ripening varieties from three different viticulture regions in Lebanon. The sampling was performed according to the guidelines of the European Commission (EC) directive in food samples (EU Commission Directive 2002/63/EC, 2002). For residue analysis, all the samples were extracted fresh as 1 Kg from each production field along two crossing diagonal transects. They were placed in polyethylene sterile bags, sealed, and labeled with a unique sample identity. They were transported to the Ministry of Agriculture: Pesticide Laboratory, Kfarchima, in a refrigerated chess box in cooled boxes (4°C). Each sample of grapes was finely homogenized using a VCM4 Waring Vertical Cutter Blender/Mixer and stored for further analysis.

2.3. Chemicals and Reagents

Pesticides analytical standards (verified purity above 98.9%) were procured from Dr. Ehrenstorfer (Augsburg, Germany) and Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH (Germany). Analytical grade solvents and reagents were obtained by Sigma-Aldrich International GmbH (Munich, Schnelldorf, Germany). Sodium chloride (NaCl), anhydrous magnesium sulfate (MgSO₄), and primary secondary amine (PSA) were supplied by Agilent Technologies (Santa Clara, CA, USA). A Milli-Q water purification system was used to obtain laboratory ultra-pure water (Millipore, Billerica, MA, USA). The stock solutions were used to prepare the individual working standard solution of each molecule 10 mg.l⁻¹. Pesticides individual stock solutions 1000 mg.l⁻¹ were prepared in acetonitrile and stored at -18 °C.

2.4. Pesticide extraction and clean-up

The extraction and clean-up method used was based on QuEChERS (Quick, Easy, Cheap, Effective, Rugged and safe) sample preparation method developed by Michelangelo Anastassiades for pesticides (Anastassiades *et al.*, 2003), followed by a clean-up procedure with dispersive-SPE.

QuEChERS procedure

Grapes with skin were finely homogenized using a VCM4 Waring Vertical Cutter Blender/Mixer (Halldé, Sweden) producing a homogeneous sample. Exactly, 10g of homogenized sample are introduced into a 50-ml Polypropylene centrifugation tube with a screw cap, which contains 10 ml acetonitrile, and shaken vigorously for 1 min. Afterward, 4 g of MgSO₄ and 1 g of NaCl are added into falcon tubes shaken vigorously, by hand, for 1 min; and then centrifuged for 5 min at 5000 rpm.

Clean-up procedure

Then a dispersive-SPE cleanup was done; transfer 1 ml of extract to a minicentrifuge tube containing 150 mg MgSO₄ and 25 mg PSA, vortex for 30 s. Centrifuged for 10 min at 3000 rpm. Finally, the supernatant was then filtered through a 0.20 µm PTFE filter and transferred into a glass vial to be analyzed by LC-MS/MS and GC-MS/MS.

2.5. Instruments, apparatus, and chromatographic conditions

Liquid Chromatography coupled to Tandem Mass Spectrometry (LC/MS-MS) analytical conditions

The LC-MS/MS analysis was performed using Agilent Technologies 1200 Infinity Series Liquid coupled to a tandem mass spectrometer. Chromatographic separation was performed with a reverse-phase analytical C₁₈ column of 150 × 2 mm and 2.5 µm particle size, Synergi (Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA) equipped with a guard-column. The LC was coupled to a 3200 QTRAP Triple Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (AB SCIEX, Dublin, CA, USA) fitted with an electrospray chemical ionization (ESI) source and operated in positive ion mode. Data acquisition was performed in multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) mode. The mobile phase consisted of a water-methanol solvent containing each 5mM ammonium acetate. The gradient program was as follows: 2% B to 100% of B over 12 min, held at 100% B until 20 min then decreased to 2% B at 25.01 min. The total run time was 30 min with a flow rate of 0.4 ml.min⁻¹. The injection volume was 5 µL and the column was maintained at 25°C. For MS/MS detection, the ion spray voltage (5 kV), and the source temperature were set at 500 °C. The collision energy (CE), the declustering potential (DP), the entrance potential (EP), and the collision cell exit potential (CXP) were optimized for each target analyte-pesticide. The collision gas and nebulizer curtain gas were nitrogen gas.

Gas Chromatography tandem Mass Spectrometry (GC/MS-MS) analytical conditions

The GC-MS/MS analysis was performed using Agilent Model 7890 gas chromatography coupled to a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer with MRM mode. Chromatographic separation was performed with Agilent HP 5Ms (5%-Phenyl)-methylpolysiloxane fused fused-silica capillary column (30 m x 0.25 mm i.d, 0.25 µm film thickness). The carrier gas was helium at a constant flow rate of 1.2 mL.min⁻¹ held by electronic pressure control. The injector port temperature was 280°C and splitless injection mode was used. The oven temperature was programmed as follows: initial temperature 100 °C (held for 1 minute) at 40 °C min⁻¹ for 240°C (held for 1min), to 300°C at 10°C min⁻¹ (held

for 4 min). The auto sampler is of type Agilent 7693 with an injection volume of 1 μ l. The ion mass spectrometer was operated in positive electron ionization mode (EI+) with an electron energy of 70 eV.

2.6. Risk Assessment

Various approaches have been utilized in this study for assessing the health risks associated with pesticide mixture exposure. This section highlights the most important approaches by determining the degree of risk to human health; an exposure evaluation was conducted based on monitoring the results of pesticide residues in grapes. The World Health Organization (WHO) divides pesticides into five classes: Ia (extremely hazardous), Ib (highly hazardous), II (moderately hazardous), III (slightly hazardous), and U (unlikely to present an acute hazard) (WHO, 2022).

Pesticides are also categorized in the pesticide properties database based on the specific human health issues they can cause, which include whether they are proven or possibly carcinogenic, genotoxic, endocrine disrupter, reproduction/development effects, an acetylcholinesterase inhibitor, neurotoxicant, respiratory tract irritant, skin irritant, skin sensitizer, eye irritant, and photo-toxicant (PPDB, 2022).

To establish the degree of risk to human health, an exposure evaluation was conducted based on monitoring the results of pesticide residues in grapes and food consumption data from the WHO/Global Environment Monitoring System-Food (WHO/GEMS/FOOD and Programme, 2006). The risk was calculated through the assessment of detected pesticide residues to the established Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) and Acute Reference (ARfD) standards developed by the Joint FAO/WHO Meeting on Pesticide residues (JMPR) database (WHO/GEMS/FOOD and Programme and G.E.M.S.F.C., 2006; WHO, 2022). Estimated Daily Intake (EDI) was calculated using the following formula:

$$EDI = \sum \frac{F_i \times MR_i}{B_w} \quad (1)$$

where EDI is the estimated daily intake in $\text{mg.kg}^{-1}.\text{day}^{-1}$, MR_i is the median residual pesticide concentration (mg.kg^{-1}), F_i is the grape daily consumption data of 15.8 g.day^{-1} (WHO/GEMS/FOOD and Programme, 2006), and B_w is the consumer body weight (60kg). In our study, the long-term exposure assessment of intake was performed by calculating the Hazard Quotient (HQ) that involves the pesticide toxicological data by calculating the ratio between the EDI and ADI according to the following formula:

$$HQ = \left(\frac{EDI}{ADI} \right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

The acceptable daily intake (ADI) is defined in mg.kg.day^{-1} . Depending on the availability, the ADI values are presented by the European Commission and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) or the Joint FAO/WHO Meeting on Pesticide Residues (JMPR). The exposed consumers were unlikely to have toxic effects if HQ exceeded 100%.

The hazard index (HI) for the multiple pesticide residues to which the consumer is exposed has been computed by summing the HQs for the multiple pesticide residues to which the consumer is exposed.

$$HI = \sum HQ \quad (3)$$

If the HI index is greater than 100%, grapes should be considered a risk to consumers, whereas if the HI index is less than 100%, grape intake should be considered acceptable.

The estimate of Short-Term Intake (ESTI) was calculated according to the following formula:

$$ESTI = \sum \frac{F_i \times HR_i}{Bw} \quad (4)$$

where F_i is the grape daily consumption data of $15.8 \text{ g}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ (WHO/GEMS/FOOD and Programme, 2006), HR_i is the highest residual concentration ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) and Bw is the consumer body weight (60kg).

The ARfD was evaluated to estimate pesticide intake in the diet. The following formula was used to calculate the acute hazard index (Hamzawy, 2022):

$$aHI = \left(\frac{ESTI}{ARfD} \right) \times 100 \quad (5)$$

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Analytical performance

An excellent linear correlation was observed, with correlation coefficient value R^2 above 0.99. The absolute recovery of each pesticide and the precision of the procedure were determined by analyzing five replicates ($n = 5$) of each type of table grape sample on different days. The recovery values in our study ranged from 76 to 98%, fulfilling the EU guidelines criteria for quantitative methods (Guidance SANTE/12682/2019, 2019). For both chromatographic techniques and all samples, repeatability, and reproducibility relative standard deviations ($RSD_r\%$ and $RSD_{Rw}\%$) were less than 20%. Finally, the signal-to-noise ratio was increased three and ten times to calculate the limits of detection (LOD) and quantitation (LOQ). In grapes, the LODs and LOQs tested were lower than the MRLs set by European legislation.

3.2. Occurrence of pesticide residues in table grape samples

The results for table grape samples collected in 2012 from diverse sampling sites in Lebanon are listed along with the frequency of detection, concentration range, and median concentrations studied, as well as the Maximum Residue Limits MRLs established by Codex Alimentarius (2012) compared to the European legislation (2022) in table grapes in **Table 1**. As shown, 44 different pesticides out of 128 formulations were found in 588 table grape samples examined under the national program routine sampling, containing 24 fungicides (54.5%), 18 insecticides (40.9%), 1 acaricide (2.3%), and 1 herbicide (2.3%). According to (Łozowicka *et al.*, 2013), fungicides were also prevalent in Poland in higher quantities than insecticides. However, contrary to what we established (Alla *et al.*, 2015), insecticides were more prevalent in Egyptian fruits.

Of the analyzed samples, 21 pesticides (47.7%) found in grapes exceeded the MRLs, while 23 pesticides were found in concentrations lower than MRLs. Specifically, 61% (11 out of 18 active ingredients) of the detected insecticides were found to exceed the MRL, while 41.7% (10 out of 24 active ingredients) of the detected fungicides were above the MRL. None of the herbicides and acaricides detected exceeded the MRL. In comparison, table grapes in the current study contained 81.54% of samples with residues below the MRL, and 18.45% above the MRL. This result is similar to the report by (Chen, 2011) which shows that only 11.7% of samples contained residues above the MRL. Similarly, according to (Antary *et al.*, 2021), Jordanian crops had residue levels that were lower than the MRL.

The presence of pesticide residues in table grapes is influenced by various factors, including the pesticide's degradation rate and application dose, as stated by (Helbling *et al.*, 2014).

Table 1. Pesticide residues found in the table grape samples.

Pesticides	No. of positive (exceeding) samples ¹	Min-Max (mg kg ⁻¹)	Median (\pm SD) ² (mg kg ⁻¹)	MRL (Table Grape)	
				2012 ³	2022 ⁴
Fungicides					
Azoxystrobin	95	0.015-1.909	0.358 (\pm 0.35)	2	3
Boscalid	58	0.040-3.167	0.978 (\pm 1.08)	5	5
Carbendazim	73 (1)	0.036-3.100	0.874 (\pm 0.66)	3	0.3
Cymoxanil	1	0.008	0.008 (\pm 0.00)	0.01	0.3
Cyproconazole	8 (3)	0.001-0.253	0.009 (\pm 0.10)	0.01	0.2
Cyprodinil	101	0.029-1.119	0.345 (\pm 0.27)	3	3
Difenoconazole	85 (15)	0.012-0.600	0.057 (\pm 0.09)	0.1	3
Dimethomorph	1	0.040	0.040 (\pm 0.00)	2	3
Fenhexamid	61	0.030-1.975	0.505 (\pm 0.54)	15	15
Flusilazole	13 (3)	0.023-1.291	0.079 (\pm 0.34)	0.2	0.01
Hexaconazole	37 (3)	0.001-0.152	0.006 (\pm 0.03)	0.01	0.01
Kresoxim-methyl	1	0.652	0.652 (\pm 0.00)	1	1.5
Metalaxyl	7	0.020-0.970	0.154 (\pm 0.35)	1	2
Metalaxyl-M	3 (3)	0.120-0.237	0.237 (\pm 0.06)	0.01	2
Myclobutanil	45	0.020-0.945	0.279 (\pm 0.33)	1	1.5
Penconazole	18	0.010-0.187	0.102 (\pm 0.06)	0.2	0.5
Procymidone	3	0.003-0.009	0.006 (\pm 0.00)	0.01	0.01
Pyraclostrobin	18	0.022-1.083	0.135 (\pm 0.31)	2	0.3
Pyrimethanil	7	0.059-1.190	0.614 (\pm 0.48)	4	5
Tetraconazole	15 (9)	0.004-0.790	0.123 (\pm 0.20)	0.01	0.5
Thiophanate-methyl	87 (66)	0.002-1.920	0.359 (\pm 0.62)	0.01	0.01
Tolclofos-methyl	7 (5)	0.006-1.620	0.150 (\pm 0.65)	0.01	0.01
Triadimenol	2 (1)	0.700-2.100	1.400 (\pm 0.98)	2	0.3
Trifloxystrobin	45	0.010-0.067	0.040 (\pm 0.01)	3	3
Insecticides					
Acetamiprid	34 (15)	0.022-0.587	0.096 (\pm 0.23)	0.5	0.5
Carbofuran	2	0.007-0.009	0.008 (\pm 0.00)	0.01	0.002
Chlorpyrifos	56 (5)	0.006-0.746	0.204 (\pm 0.20)	0.5	0.01
Chlorpyrifos-methyl	1	0.142	0.142 (\pm 0.00)	1	0.01
Cypermethrin	75 (48)	0.005-1.774	0.365 (\pm 0.39)	0.2	0.5
Deltamethrin	4 (1)	0.100-0.246	0.155 (\pm 0.06)	0.2	0.2
Diflubenzuron	1	0.008	0.008 (\pm 0.00)	0.01	0.01
Dimethoate	4 (2)	0.006-0.165	0.067 (\pm 0.08)	0.01	0.01
Etoxazole	1	0.090	0.090 (\pm 0.00)	0.5	0.5
Flufenoxuron	4 (4)	0.141-0.543	0.269 (\pm 0.18)	0.01	0.01
Imidacloprid	24 (1)	0.039-1.290	0.310 (\pm 0.36)	1	1
Indoxacarb	43	0.020-0.979	0.100 (\pm 0.28)	2	2
Lambda-cyhalothrin	2 (2)	0.360-0.400	0.380 (\pm 0.03)	0.01	0.08
Lufenuron	19 (8)	0.006-0.404	0.008 (\pm 0.16)	0.01	0.01

Methamidophos	1 (1)	0.150	0.150 (\pm 0.00)	0.01	0.01
Methomyl	2	0.164-0.194	0.179 (\pm 0.02)	0.3	0.01
Pirimiphos-methyl	1	0.003	0.003 (\pm 0.00)	0.01	0.01
Pyridaben	16 (4)	0.001-0.137	0.007 (\pm 0.05)	0.01	0.01
Acaricide					
Propargite	2	2.000-2.800	2.400 (\pm 0.56)	7	0.01
Herbicide					
Fluazifop-butyl	1	0.009	0.090 (\pm 0.00)	0.01	0.01

¹Number of samples exceeding the EU-MRLs are given between brackets; ² Mean (\pm SD) Standard Deviation; ³ MRL = Maximum Residue Level according to Codex Alimentarius; ⁴ MRL according to European legislation

The percentage of positive irregular samples ($>$ MRL) detected in table grapes assessed during the survey in the three major agricultural regions is listed in **Table 2**. The highest percentage of irregularity was for thiophanate-methyl (6.09%), cypermethrin (4.43%), difenoconazole (1.38%), acetamiprid (1.38%), tetraconazole (0.83%), and lufenuron (0.73%). According to the EU Pesticides database, it was observed that six pesticides from the detected pesticides were not approved on grapes in 2012 and these pesticides were carbofuran, flufenoxuron, flusilazole, hexaconazole, methamidophos, procymidone, and propargite. Only flufenoxuron, flusilazole, and hexaconazole showed values above MRL. In addition, it was noted that there are four pesticides restricted in Lebanon: chlorpyrifos-methyl, cypermethrin, kresoxim-methyl, and pyridaben which are still authorized by the European Union. Among them, cypermethrin and pyridaben, belonging to pyrethroid and pyridazinone, have values above MRL. Since 2012, according to codex and EU commission some MRLs were modified for pesticides that pose a risk to consumer's health, and banned from the European Commission (*EU Pesticides Database*, 2022); as carbendazim, chlorpyrifos, chlorpyrifos-methyl, diflubenzuron, dimethoate, lufenuron, methomyl, thiophanate-methyl, and triadimenol. Although carbendazim has been banned since 2014, the relevant metabolite of thiophanate-methyl was still authorized until 2019. The unauthorized carbendazim was found in this study, in which it was detected in 6.73% of the samples at a mean concentration of 0.874 mg.kg⁻¹. When compared to carbendazim residues in grape leaves the mean concentration detected (0.874 mg.kg⁻¹) is higher than 0.765 mg.kg⁻¹ (Hamzawy, 2022), respectively. While pyridaben was detected in 1.47% at a mean concentration of 0.007 mg.kg⁻¹. Excessive use of pesticides on grapes for which they were either registered or not registered; disrespect of specified preharvest intervals (PHI); and, in addition, application rates typically exceeded manufacturers' recommendations in the assumption that more is preferable for pest management. The detected pesticides with values above MRL were as follows: Thiophanate-methyl from 0.002 - 1.920 mg.kg⁻¹, difenoconazole from 0.012 - 0.600 mg.kg⁻¹, cypermethrin from 0.005 - 1.774 mg.kg⁻¹, and acetamiprid from 0.022 - 0.587 mg.kg⁻¹.

Table 2. Distribution, detection frequency (%), and median (mg kg⁻¹) of the detected residues exceeding the Codex Alimentarius MRL.

Molecules	Location					
	Beqaa Valley			North Lebanon		
	Detection Frequency (%)	Median (± SD) ¹ (mg kg ⁻¹)	Residues > MRL (%) ²	Detection Frequency (%)	Median (± SD) (mg kg ⁻¹)	Residues > MRL (%)
Thiophanate-methyl	52.9	0.637 (± 0.65)	40.2	47.1	0.167 (± 0.54)	35.6
Cypermethrin	88	0.285 (± 0.35)	52	12	0.567 (± 0.52)	12
Acetamiprid	64.7	0.099 (± 0.23)	29.4	35.3	0.081 (± 0.24)	14.7
Difenoconazole	78.8	0.057 (± 0.04)	10.6	21.2	0.084 (± 0.16)	7.1
Tetraconazole	86.7	0.135 (± 0.21)	60	13.3	0.006 (± 0.00)	ND
Lufenuron	94.7	0.007 (± 0.17)	36.8	5.3	0.266 (± 0.00)	5.3
Tolclofos-methyl	100	0.150 (± 0.65)	71.4	ND	ND	ND
Chlorpyrifos	64.3	0.185 (± 0.19)	5.4	35.7	0.216 (± 0.19)	3.6
Flufenoxuron	100	0.196 (± 0.18)	100	ND	ND	ND
Pyridaben	56.3	0.004 (± 0.04)	6.3	43.8	0.008 (± 0.06)	18.8
Metalaxyl-M	66.7	0.178 (± 0.08)	66.7	33.3	0.237 (± 0.00)	33.3
Cyproconazole	78.2	0.009 (± 0.10)	ND	ND	ND	ND
Flusilazole	92.3	0.083 (± 0.35)	23.1	7.7	0.04 (± 0.00)	ND
Hexaconazole	64.9	0.006 (± 0.00)	ND	35.1	0.008 (± 0.06)	8.1
Lambda-cyhalothrin	ND	ND	ND	100	0.380 (± 0.02)	100
Dimethoate	25	0.165 (± 0.00)	25	75	0.007 (± 0.07)	25
Methamidophos	ND	ND	ND	100	0.15 (± 0.00)	100
Triadimenol	ND	ND	ND	100	1.400 (± 0.99)	50
Deltamethrin	100	0.155 (± 0.06)	25	ND	ND	ND
Imidacloprid	83.3	0.328 (± 0.36)	4.2	16.7	0.108 (± 0.03)	ND
Carbendazim	54.8	0.770 (± 0.75)	1.4	45.2	1.021 (± 0.54)	ND

¹ Mean ±SD: Standard Deviation; ² Percentage of residues exceeding the MRL

The most frequently detected pesticide was the fungicide cyprodinil, with a detection rate of (17.2%), followed by azoxystrobin (16.2%), thiophanate-methyl (14.8%), difenoconazole (14.5%), then by insecticide cypermethrin (12.8%), the fungicide carbendazim (12.4%), fenhexamid (10.4%), boscalid (9.9%), and the insecticide chlorpyrifos (9.5%) **Figure 2**. Because of the expected fungal diseases that will affect fruits, particularly grapes, this may reflect the extensive use of fungicides, which is compatible with the behavior of fruits pest control. Although cyprodinil was detected in most of the samples with concentration ranging from 0.028 - 1.119 mg.kg⁻¹, no samples contained concentrations above the pesticide's MRL. Pesticide residues found in this survey matched those found in other studies, Kostek (Kostik, 2014) indicated that cyprodinil is a commonly detected pesticide in table grapes with levels less than EU-MRLs. Likewise, none of the samples containing azoxystrobin, a broad-spectrum systemic fungicide extensively used in agriculture to protect plants from fungal diseases and the most often found pesticide in this investigation, had levels above MRL, with concentration range of 0.016 to 1.909 mg.kg⁻¹. These frequencies of detection was similar in study conducted in Turkey, it was observed that azoxystrobin, carbendazim, chlorpyrifos, cyprodinil, indoxacarb, and boscalid are the most detected pesticides in fruit samples, mostly found in grapes (43%) (Kazar Soydan *et al.*, 2021).

The persistence of the fungicides myclobutanil, metalaxyl, and trifloxystrobin in wine have been highlighted by many authors (Angioni et al., 2011; Angioni & Dedola, 2013; Cabras & Angioni, 2000). The findings of this study are analogous to those of pesticide monitoring programs conducted worldwide. In Brazil, difeconazole and cypermethrin were the main compounds detected in the monitoring program (Jardim, 2012). To date, no studies on pesticide residues in table grapes have been reported in Lebanon. For Lebanese apple samples, similar pesticide residues, such as chlorpyrifos, lambda-cyhalothrin, myclobutanil, and cypermethrin were detected (El Hawari *et al.*, 2019). Chlorpyrifos was found to be less frequently present in this study than in investigations by Amoah (Amoah *et al.*, 2006) and Blankson (Blankson, 2016), which reported that 78% and 22.2% of the leafy vegetable samples they studied, respectively, were contaminated with the pesticide.

Figure 2. The percentage of table grape samples with residues below, equal, and above the MRLs.

The main goal of this study was to determine the presence and distribution of pesticides in three major agricultural regions. The reason for the investigations in these three regions was that they are the largest agricultural areas in Lebanon that produce the majority of table and wine grapes. **Figure 3** shows the distribution of pesticides in

the three agricultural regions. The percentages of samples produced from the Beqaa Valley, North Lebanon, and South Lebanon were 79.76%, 17.35%, and 2.89%, respectively. The Beqaa Valley, which has long been regarded as the ideal region to produce wine grapes, continues to be the area with the highest concentration, followed by North Lebanon (Mohasseb *et al.*, 2020). Most farmers in the Beqaa Valley and North Lebanon regions have minimal levels of education and receive inadequate technical support; therefore, they do not read or understand pesticide labels, since English is the language used on most imported pesticide warnings and are economically vulnerable. The existence of non-authorized use in Lebanon found in this study is attributable in part to the agricultural population's profile and the lack of phytosanitary support provided to crop varieties (Abou Zeid *et al.*, 2020). We have noticed a high level of pesticide abuse in the Beqaa Valley and North Lebanon. These pesticides are used in this zone with minimal regulation, especially near the Syrian border, since farmers are tempted to choose low cost and high efficiency over environmental implications (El-Osmani *et al.*, 2014). In cold areas like Beqaa Valley-Zale, a more effective protection approach against grapevine diseases is needed, and as a result, most pesticide residues were detected (Kostik, 2014). Likewise, honey has been proven an effective environmental bio indicator of pesticide contamination in several studies. Honey samples contaminated with pesticides have been found near rural areas known for agricultural output, such as the Akkar Valley, which has shown that most are contaminated with pesticide residues (Al Alam *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 3. Distribution of the detected residues among the Lebanese agricultural regions.

Imidacloprid is a neonicotinoid systemic insecticide that is currently the most widely used insecticide (Čuš *et al.*, 2010). Despite its widespread use, imidacloprid residues exceeded the MRL (1.29 mg/kg) in one of the 24 positive samples. While chlorpyrifos is an organophosphate pesticide with considerable human toxicity, chlorpyrifos was detected in 51 grape samples below the MRL. Only five samples exceeded the MRL at a concentration of 0.706 ± 0.04 . Among fungicides, triazole was most frequently detected (20.57%), followed by benzimidazole (15.40%), strobilurin (14.66%), anilinopyrimidine (9.96%) and (12.36%) for other fungicides. For insecticides, (7.5%) of the detected samples were contaminated by pyrethroids, organophosphate (5.81%), neonicotinoid (5.35%), and with (8.2%) for other insecticides. Only 0.28% of the acaricide and herbicide-contaminated samples contain sulphite ester and aryloxyphenoxypropionate, respectively **Figure 4**. Organophosphates and pyrethroids are the most commonly found pesticide groups in Egyptian and Ghana fruits and vegetables, as evidenced by earlier studies (GadAlla, Thabet and Salama, 2013; Alla *et al.*, 2015; Blankson, 2016). In-depth chemical modifications made during the development of synthetic pyrethroids make these substances more hazardous and less environment degradable. As a result, there

are likely to be several routes of exposure to pyrethroid pesticides, including agricultural treatments and home pest management. Pyrethroids are among the least toxic pesticides, but even so, they can have negative consequences such as liver function impairment, respiratory issues, and endocrine disruption when used repeatedly. Some underlying mechanisms of toxicity include allergic reaction, oxidative stress, and lipid peroxidation (Abou El-Magd, Sabik and Shoukry, 2011).

Among the organochlorine pesticides studied, such as DDT, HCH, and their metabolites, which can persist in food for a long period of time, and have toxic effects on fauna, flora, and humans (Sudaryanto *et al.*, 2007), none is detected in the Lebanese samples. In Brazil, triazoles, pyrethroids, and organophosphorus classes were predominantly found in grapes (Jardim and Caldas, 2012). Among the detected triazoles, difenoconazole was one of the most common pesticides detected in Lebanese table grapes. Difenoconazole has been the most frequent triazole identified in food samples in Brazil (Jardim and Caldas, 2012) and Belgium (Claeys *et al.*, 2011). In the Danish surveillance from 2004 to 2007, chlorpyrifos was the most common organophosphorus compound detected in fruits and vegetables (Jensen, Petersen and Christensen, 2009). Similar results were found in Egypt, where fungicides predominated in table grapes and boscalid was one of the most frequently detected residues (Eissa *et al.*, 2013). Organophosphates, pyrethroids, and neonicotinoids have been the most often detected pesticides that have exceeded MRLs, according to studies in Uganda, Egypt, Ghana and Poland (Szpyrka, 2015; Fosu *et al.*, 2017; Issa, 2018; Fuhrmann, 2021). The results also showed that among the 44 pesticides detected, 68.2% were systemic and 31.8% had a contact mode of action.

Figure 4. Pesticide residues distribution according to their chemical family.

Each year, two or more pesticide residues are discovered in cultivated food samples that are highly susceptible to pests, because different classes of pesticides must be applied to minimize pest resistance, protect the crops, and have good yields (Eissa *et al.*, 2013). On the other extreme, multiple residues could imply that that Good Agricultural

Practices (GAP) are not being practiced. The number of different pesticides in a single sample ranged from 1 to 7 **Figure 5**. Although the consumption rate of grapes ($15.8 \text{ g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{person}^{-1}$) is low, the presence of several pesticide residues in raw fruits makes it important to take major precautions while eating them. (Latif, 2011; Adjrah *et al.*, 2013) have raised major concerns about the overuse and random combination of several groups of pesticides, which can result in the development of resistance in crop pests. No residues were detected in 2.55%, on the other hand, 47.45% of the samples in which only one pesticide was detected, 26.19% of samples contained two, 15.31% of samples contain three residues, and 5% of samples contained four residues. Additionally, 2.4, 0.85, and 0.17% of samples were contaminated with 5, 6, and 7 pesticides, respectively. The overall rate of samples with several residues was the same as the rates of samples with no residue and samples with a single residue. One or two fungicides and one or two insecticides were frequently present together in co-existing chemical residues. Most samples included two or more pesticide residues, and sample numbers decreased as the number of residues increased. In some grape samples, there were up to seven different pesticides identified. The presence of highest number multiresidues in some grape samples in Lebanon has been also reported by Nasreddine *et al.* (Nasreddine *et al.*, 2016).

The lack of pesticide residues in a small number of table grape samples can be attributed to those farmers who concerned about the problem of pesticide residues and used scientific methods to limit pesticide usage or choose for environmentally friendly preventative and control measures. The findings are consistent with many other studies. Table grapes had the highest prevalence of multiple residues in unprocessed foods (over 66.1%) in the EU Program (European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), Carrasco Cabrera and Medina Pastor, 2021). In Canada (Ripley *et al.*, 2000), Egypt (Dogheim, Alla and El-Marsafy, 2001), Brazil (Jardim *et al.*, 2014), Poland (Szpyrka, 2015) and Turkey (Kazar Soydan *et al.*, 2021) grape samples were reported to contain over five different pesticide residues. Multiple residues are expected in some crops since the treatment should vary between pesticide classes to reduce pest resistance. Multiple residues, though, could also be an indication of disrespect for the principles of good agricultural practice (Jardim, 2012).

Figure 5. The number of detectable residues detected in each sample of table grapes.

3.3. Human Risk Assessment

A human risk evaluation was used to evaluate the negative impacts of pesticides on Lebanese citizens. **Table 3** demonstrates that none of the 44 pesticides detected are WHO class (Ia - Extremely Hazardous). Despite being categorized as highly harmful (class Ib), carbofuran, chlorpyrifos, methamidophos, and methyl were all banned in the EU and thereafter in Lebanon in 2016, 2020, 2010, and 2019, respectively (Ministry of Agriculture (MoA), 2022). However, 38.63% are moderately harmful (class II), and 15.90% are slightly hazardous (class III). Additionally, 22.72% of the ones examined are unlikely to present acute hazards (class U) and 13.63% are not yet listed.

It is important to realize that MRLs are not definitive safety limits; food residues can have levels above MRLs while still being safe for consumption (Keikotthaile and Spanoghe, 2010). In this situation, the legally established "Maximum Residue Limits" (MRL) are not a guarantee of "zero health risk," but only indicators of the violation or non-violation of good agricultural practices (GAP), not an indication of health hazard. Acute Reference Dose (ARD) or Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) are two toxicological end points that should be used to evaluate risk exposure (ARfD) (Alla *et al.*, 2015). A long-term exposure assessment for detected pesticides was used to estimate the risk of pesticide residues in grapes. **Table 3** proves that the proposed daily consumption (EDI) of the forty-four pesticide residues is low when compared to the ADI. The presence of these residues in grapes indicates that consumers are exposed to multiple pesticides at once, each of which has a similar mechanism of toxicity. As a result, we calculated a cumulative risk for a mixture of pesticides in our study by summing the HQs to get the hazard index (HI).

The HI for residues was 55.66%, which was below 100%, indicating that cumulative exposure to these pesticides poses negligible health risk to consumers. We can conclude from the obtained results that the pesticides detected in the Lebanese grapes are not hazardous to consumers. However, due to the possibility of cumulative exposure to chemicals from diverse foods and pesticide use in agriculture, caution should be taken. The %HQ was in the range of 0.002 – 23.6% of the ADI's. The highest exposure was observed for two carbamates: propargite (9.03% of ADI) and methomyl (23.6% of the ADI). These pesticides are only detected in four samples out of the 588 samples. However, chlorpyrifos, an organophosphorus that might affect the central nervous system by inhibiting the activity of the enzyme acetylcholinesterase (Dhull *et al.*, 2013), was shown to have HQ = 5.37%. The presence of a mixture of pesticides with high HQ in grapes indicates that consumers are exposed to multiple pesticides simultaneously, a few of which could have a similar toxicity mechanism. This is the reason we estimated a cumulative risk for a pesticide mixture in our study by adding the HQs to generate the hazard index (HI).

Short-term exposure assessment was investigated via calculations of ESTI for carcinogenic risk assessment and comparing the results with AfRD to find aHI. The results showed that the overall aHI was less than 100%. This means that an exposure assessment based on pesticide residue levels found in the table grapes investigated in this research confirms that consuming the examined samples in Lebanon poses no health risk. Adult health is not endangered by fruit consumption, according to similar research conducted in Brazil, China, and Poland (Jardim *et al.*, 2014; Lozowicka, 2015; Szyrka, 2015; Zhixia, Nie and Yan, 2018). When two or more chemicals or other compounds produce the same, or nearly the same, sequence of significant biochemical events, they are said to have a same mechanism of toxicity. Organophosphorus (OPs), carbamate (CBs), and pyrethroid (PPs) are three classes of pesticides that have been classified by the USEPA as belonging to the same cumulative assessment group and with a

similar mechanism of toxicity (USEPA, 2018). In this survey, five OPs (chlorpyrifos, chlorpyrifos-methyl, dimethoate, methamidophos, and pirimiphos-methyl), two CBs (carbofuran and methomyl), and three PPs (cypermethrin, deltamethrin, and lambda-cyhalothrin) were involved to evaluate the cumulative dietary exposure. The cumulative chronic risks of the three families were 39.09% of the total %HQ, they are far below 100% which within the acceptable level.

Table 3. WHO classification and total exposure of ADI, ARfD, ESTI, Hazard Quotient and Acute Hazard Index of detected pesticides in table grapes.

Molecule	WHO Classification	ADI	EDI	Hazard	ARfD	ESTI	Acute Hazard Index (%)
		Mg kg ⁻¹ Bw day ⁻¹	Mg kg ⁻¹ Bw day ⁻¹	Quotient (%)			
Contact Mode of Action							
Chlorpyrifos	Ib	0.001	5.37E-05	5.37	NA	1.96E-04	NA
Chlorpyrifos-methyl	III	0.010	3.74E-05	0.37	0.100	3.74E-05	0.04
Cypermethrin	II	0.050	9.61E-05	0.19	0.200	4.67E-04	0.23
Deltamethrin	II	0.010	4.08E-05	0.41	0.010	6.48E-05	0.65
Diflubenzuron	III	0.100	2.11E-06	0.00	NA	2.11E-06	NA
Etoxazole	NL	0.040	2.37E-05	0.06	NA	2.37E-05	NA
Flufenoxuron	III	0.010	7.08E-05	0.71	0.010	1.43E-04	1.43
Indoxacarb	II	0.006	2.63E-05	0.44	0.004	2.58E-04	6.45
Kresoxim-methyl	NL	0.400	1.72E-04	0.04	NA	1.72E-04	NA
Lambda-cyhalothrin	II	0.002	1.00E-04	5.00	0.001	1.05E-04	16.72
Pirimiphos-methyl	U	0.004	7.90E-07	0.02	0.020	7.90E-07	0.00
Propargite	III	0.007	6.32E-04	9.03	0.030	7.37E-04	2.46
Pyraclostrobin	NL	0.030	3.56E-05	0.12	0.015	2.85E-04	1.90
Pyridaben	II	0.010	1.84E-06	0.02	0.005	3.61E-05	0.72
Pyrimethanil	II	0.170	1.62E-04	0.10	0.120	3.13E-04	0.26
Tolclofos-methyl	U	0.064	3.95E-05	0.06	0.064	4.27E-04	0.67
Systemic Mode of Action							
Acetamiprid	NL	0.025	2.53E-05	0.10	0.025	1.55E-04	0.62
Azoxystrobin	U	0.200	9.43E-05	0.05	NA	5.03E-04	NA
Boscalid	U	0.040	2.58E-04	0.64	NA	8.34E-04	NA
Carbendazim	U	0.020	2.30E-04	1.15	0.020	8.16E-04	4.08
Carbofuran	Ib	1.5E-04	2.11E-06	1.40	0.00015	2.37E-06	NA
Cymoxanil	II	0.013	2.11E-06	0.02	0.080	2.11E-06	0.00
Cyproconazole	II	0.020	2.37E-06	0.01	0.020	6.66E-05	0.33
Cyprodinil	NL	0.030	9.09E-05	0.30	NA	6.66E-05	NA
Difenoconazole	II	0.010	1.50E-05	0.15	0.160	1.58E-04	0.10
Dimethoate	II	0.001	1.76E-05	1.76	NA	4.35E-05	NA
Dimethomorph	II	0.050	1.05E-05	0.02	0.600	1.05E-05	0.00
Fenhexamid	U	0.200	1.33E-04	0.07	0.200	5.20E-04	0.26
Fluazifop-butyl	III	NA	2.37E-06	NA	NA	2.37E-06	NA
Flusilazole	II	0.002	2.08E-05	1.04	0.005	3.40E-04	6.80
Hexaconazole	III	0.005	1.58E-06	0.03	NA	4.00E-05	NA
Imidacloprid	II	0.060	8.16E-05	0.14	0.080	3.40E-04	0.42

Lufenuron	NL	0.015	2.11E-06	0.01	0.010	1.06E-04	1.06
Metalaxyl	II	0.080	4.06E-05	0.05	0.080	2.55E-04	0.32
Metalaxyl-M	II	0.080	6.24E-05	0.08	0.080	6.24E-05	0.08
Methamidophos	Ib	0.004	3.95E-05	0.99	0.010	3.95E-05	0.40
Methomyl	Ib	0.002	4.71E-04	23.57	0.003	5.11E-05	2.04
Myclobutanil	II	0.025	7.35E-05	0.29	0.030	2.49E-04	0.83
Penconazole	III	0.030	2.69E-05	0.09	0.030	4.92E-05	0.16
Procymidone	U	0.002	1.58E-06	0.08	0.012	2.37E-06	0.02
Tetraconazole	II	0.004	3.24E-05	0.81	0.030	2.08E-04	0.69
Thiophanate-methyl	U	0.080	9.45E-05	0.12	0.080	5.06E-04	0.63
Triadimenol	II	0.050	3.69E-04	0.74	0.050	5.53E-04	1.11
Trifloxystrobin	U	0.100	1.05E-05	0.01	0.060	1.76E-05	0.03

Toxicological and human health effect profiles are being used to categorize pesticides (PPDB, 2022). The pesticides identified were either: (1) classified as carcinogenic, mutagenic, or reprotoxic; (2) identified as potential endocrine disruptors; (3) identified as acetylcholinesterase inhibitors; (4) classified as respiratory tract irritants; (5) identified as neurotoxins; or (6) associated with skin sensitization and irritation, and eye irritation **Figure 6**. We first highlight that a variety of residues may simultaneously contribute to a range of health problems. The database shows that 36.4% and 29.5% of the 44 detected residues can cause eye and skin irritation, respectively, while respiratory tract irritation (inhalation exposure) and skin sensitizers are caused by 34% and 22.7% of residues, respectively. However, based on the data analysis of the databases, we established that 31.8% of residues could affect human development and/or reproduction. Additionally, 9% of residues are probably neurotoxic and endocrine disruptors. However, carcinogenic and acetylcholinesterase inhibitory residues only represent 2.2% and nearly 13.6% of residues, respectively, while 27.2% of the residues have the tendency to be mutagenic for humans. Consequently, pesticide residue management and monitoring, as well as food safety awareness, should be improved. Public awareness should be increased to urge people to wash their food properly and regularly to eliminate or limit the adverse effects of pesticide residues on humans.

Figure 6. Health issues resulting from the detected active molecules according to PPDB.

4. Conclusion

Overall, 44 pesticide residues belonging to various chemical groups were detected in table grape samples collected during routine analysis from vineyards in Lebanese agricultural areas. Some of the pesticides were registered in Lebanon in 2012, but now they are banned for agricultural activities. The triazole, strobilurin, and benzimidazole chemical groups, which belong to the fungicide functional class, are the most detected pesticides. The cocktail of pesticide residue could be considered a public health problem because the table grapes are eaten raw. When following the recommended application of WHO guidelines, pesticide residues detected above the MRL are unlikely to present significant health concerns to the Lebanese population because the short-term (HI) and long-term (cHI) risk indices are below 100%. The Lebanese Ministry of Agriculture is continuing to monitor pesticide residues in table and wine grapes to reduce health risks to consumers, as well as assessing awareness campaigns on proper pesticide use for farmers to have good agricultural practice, considering pre-harvest intervals (PHI) to avoid pesticide residue concentrations in food products exceeding the EU MRL values.

5. References

- Abou El-Magd, S.A., Sabik, L.M.E. and Shoukry, A. (2011) 'Pyrethroid Toxic Effects on some Hormonal Profile and Biochemical Markers among Workers in Pyrethroid Insecticides Company', 8(1), p. 12.
- Abou Zeid, M.I. *et al.* (2020) 'Suggested policy and legislation reforms to reduce deleterious effect of pesticides in Lebanon', *Heliyon*, 6(12), p. e05524. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e05524>.
- Abu Ghyda, T. and Fahs, D. (2007) 'EFTA/Swiss project on protection of Geographical Indications in Lebanon', p. 15. Available at: <https://www.economy.gov.lb/en/projects/protection-of-geographical-indications>.

Adjrah, Y. *et al.* (2013) 'Survey of pesticide application on vegetables in the Littoral area of Togo', *Annals of Agricultural and Environmental Medicine*, 20(4), p. 6.

Al Alam, J. *et al.* (2017) 'The use of honey as environmental biomonitor of pesticides contamination in northern Lebanon', *Euro-Mediterranean Journal for Environmental Integration*, 2(1), p. 23. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41207-017-0034-9>.

Alavanja, M.C.R., Ross, M.K. and Bonner, M.R. (2013) 'Increased cancer burden among pesticide applicators and others due to pesticide exposure: Pesticides Exposure and Cancer', *CA: A Cancer Journal for Clinicians*, 63(2), pp. 120–142. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3322/caac.21170>.

Alla, S.A.G. *et al.* (2015) 'Evaluation of Pesticide Residues in some Egyptian Fruits', 04(01), pp. 87–97.

Amoah, P. *et al.* (2006) 'Pesticide and Pathogen Contamination of Vegetables in Ghana's Urban Markets', (5), pp. 1–6. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00244-004-0054-8>.

Anastassiades, M. *et al.* (2003) 'Fast and Easy Multiresidue Method Employing Acetonitrile Extraction/Partitioning and "Dispersive Solid-Phase Extraction" for the Determination of Pesticide Residues in Produce', *Journal of AOAC INTERNATIONAL*, 86(2), pp. 412–431. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jaoac/86.2.412>.

Angioni, A. *et al.* (2011) 'Fate of Iprovalicarb, Indoxacarb, and Boscalid Residues in Grapes and Wine by GC-ITMS Analysis', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, (59), pp. 6806–6812. Available at: <https://doi.org/dx.doi.org/10.1021/jf2011672>.

Angioni, A. and Dedola, F. (2013) 'Three years monitoring survey of pesticide residues in Sardinia wines following integrated pest management strategies', *Environ Monit Assess*, pp. 4281–4289. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-012-2868-6>.

Antary, T.M.A. *et al.* (2021) 'Assessment of Pesticide Residues in Crops in Northern Districts of Jordan in 2019 and 2020', 28(9), p. 15.

Antoun, L.B. (2014) 'WINE INDUSTRY IN THE BEKAA VALLEY, LEBANON FOOD-PROCESSING INDUSTRY AS A BASIS FOR COMMUNITY DYNAMICS AND LOCAL SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT', 2, p. 13. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2014.v10n10p%25p>.

Bempah, C.K. and Donkor, A.K. (2011) 'Pesticide residues in fruits at the market level in Accra Metropolis, Ghana, a preliminary study', *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 175(1–4), pp. 551–561. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-010-1550-0>.

Blankson, G.K. (2016) 'Contamination levels of organophosphorus and synthetic pyrethroid pesticides in vegetables marketed in Accra, Ghana', *Food Control*, (68), pp. 174–180. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2016.03.045>.

Cabras, P. and Angioni, A. (2000) 'Pesticide Residues in Grapes, Wine, and Their Processing Products', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 48(4), pp. 967–973. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf990727a>.

Cecchi, A. *et al.* (2012) 'Environmental exposure to organophosphate pesticides: Assessment of endocrine disruption and hepatotoxicity in pregnant women', *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 80, pp. 280–287. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2012.03.008>.

Chen, C. (2011) 'Evaluation of pesticide residues in fruits and vegetables from Xiamen, China', *Food Control*, (22), pp. 1114–1120. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2011.01.007>.

Claeys, W.L. *et al.* (2011) 'Exposure of several Belgian consumer groups to pesticide residues through fresh fruit and vegetable consumption', *Food Control*, 22(3–4), pp. 508–516. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2010.09.037>.

Codex Alimentarius Commission (2022) *Joint FAO/WHO food standards programme, food and agriculture organisation, codex pesticides residues in food online database*. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/fao-who-codexalimentarius/home/en/> (Accessed: 2 May 2022).

Čuš, F. *et al.* (2010) 'Pesticide residues and microbiological quality of bottled wines', *Food Control*, 21(2), pp. 150–154. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2009.04.010>.

Dhull, V. *et al.* (2013) 'Acetylcholinesterase Biosensors for Electrochemical Detection of Organophosphorus Compounds: A Review', *Biochemistry Research International*, 2013, pp. 1–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/731501>.

Dogheim, S.M., Alla, S.A.G. and El-Marsafy, A.M. (2001) 'Monitoring of Pesticide Residues in Egyptian Fruits and Vegetables During 1996', p. 13. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jaoac/84.2.519>.

Dohadwala, M.M. and Vita, J.A. (2009) 'Grapes and Cardiovascular Disease', *The Journal of Nutrition*, 139(9), pp. 1788S–1793S. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3945/jn.109.107474>.

EFSA (2022) *The 2017 European Union report on pesticide residues in food*. Available at: <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.2903/j.efsa.2019.5743> (Accessed: 14 May 2022).

Eissa, F.I. *et al.* (2013) 'Monitoring of multi-class pesticide residues in green grape and their potential risk for Egyptian consumer.' Available at: <http://www.sciencepub.net/nature>.

El Hawari, K. *et al.* (2019) 'Pesticide residues in Lebanese apples and health risk assessment', *Food Additives & Contaminants: Part B*, 12(2), pp. 81–89. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19393210.2018.1564370>.

El-Osmani, R. *et al.* (2014) 'Solid Phase Extraction of Organochlorine Pesticides Residues in Groundwater (Akkar Plain, North Lebanon)'

EU Commission Directive 2002/63/EC, F. (2002) *Commission Directive 2002/63/EC establishing Community methods of sampling for the official control of pesticide residues in and on products of plant and animal origin and repealing Directive 79/700/EEC*. | *UNEP Law and Environment Assistance Platform*. Available at: <https://leap.unep.org/countries/eu/national-legislation/commission-directive-200263ec-establishing-community-methods> (Accessed: 7 May 2022).

EU Pesticides Database (2022). Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database/mrls/?event=search.pr> (Accessed: 24 April 2022).

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), Carrasco Cabrera, L. and Medina Pastor, P. (2021) 'The 2019 European Union report on pesticide residues in food', *EFSA Journal*, 19(4). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2021.6491>.

Fahed, C. and Hayar, S. (2021) 'Conventional vs. Organic Cucumber Production in Lebanon: Risk Assessment of the Recommended Agrochemicals on Consumer Health and the Environment', *Chemistry Africa*, 4(2), pp. 463–476. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42250-021-00238-8>.

Faostat, F. (2021) *Statistical databases. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations*. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#home>. (Accessed: 2 May 2022).

Fosu, P.O. *et al.* (2017) ‘Surveillance of pesticide residues in fruits and vegetables from Accra Metropolis markets, Ghana, 2010–2012: a case study in Sub-Saharan Africa’, *Environ Sci Pollut Res*, (24), pp. 17187–17205. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-017-9287-8>.

Frem, M. *et al.* (2021) ‘The potential direct economic impact and private management costs of an invasive alien species: *Xylella fastidiosa* on Lebanese wine grapes’, *NeoBiota*, 70, pp. 43–67. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3897/neobiota.70.72280>.

Fuhrmann, S. (2021) ‘Exposure to multiple pesticides and neurobehavioral outcomes among smallholder farmers in Uganda’, *Environment International*, (152), p. 106477. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106477>.

GadAlla, S.A., Thabet, W.M. and Salama, E.Y. (2013) ‘Monitoring and Risk Assessment of Pesticide Residues in Some Egyptian Vegetables’, p. 15.

González-Rodríguez, R.M. (2009) ‘Multiresidue determination of 11 new fungicides in grapes and wines by liquid–liquid extraction/clean-up and programmable temperature vaporization injection with analyte protectants/gas chromatography/ion trap mass spectrometry’, *Journal of Chromatography A*, 1216(32), pp. 6033–6042. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2009.06.046>.

Guidance SANTE/12682/2019 (2019) *Guidance Document on Analytical Quality Control and Method Validation Procedures for Pesticides Residues Analysis in Food and Feed*. Available at: <https://www.accredia.it/en/documento/guidance-sante-12682-2019-guidance-document-on-analytical-quality-control-and-method-validation-procedures-for-pesticides-residues-analysis-in-food-and-feed/> (Accessed: 29 November 2022).

Hamzawy, A.H. (2022) ‘Residual pesticides in grape leaves (*Vitis vinifera L.*) on the Egyptian market and human health risk’, *Food Additives & Contaminants: Part B*, 15(1), pp. 62–70. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19393210.2021.2022005>.

Hayar, S., Zeitoun, R. and Maestroni, B.M. (2021) ‘Validation of a Rapid Multiresidue Method for the Determination of Pesticide Residues in Vine Leaves. Comparison of the Results According to the Different Conservation Methods’, *Molecules*, 26(4), p. 1176. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26041176>.

Helbling, D.E. *et al.* (2014) ‘Kinetics and yields of pesticide biodegradation at low substrate concentrations and under assimilable organic carbon (AOC)-restricted conditions’, p. 31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.03622-13>.

Imran, M. *et al.* (2017) ‘Health Benefits of Grapes Polyphenols’, *Agricultural Sciences*, 10, p. 13.

Issa, A.B. (2018) ‘Risk assessment of some organic contaminants: a case study based on food consumption in Tanta and Ismailia cities, Egypt’, *Environ Sci Pollut Res*, (25), pp. 34212–34220. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-018-3313-3>.

Jardim, A.N.O. (2012) ‘Brazilian monitoring programs for pesticide residues in food - Results from 2001 to 2010’, *Food Control*, pp. 607–616. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2011.11.001>.

Jardim, A.N.O. *et al.* (2014) ‘Pesticide residues in cashew apple, guava, kaki and peach: GC–IECD, GC–FPD and LC–MS/MS multiresidue method validation, analysis and cumulative acute risk assessment’, *Food Chemistry*, (164), pp. 195–204. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2014.05.030>.

Jardim, A.N.O. and Caldas, E.D. (2012) ‘Brazilian monitoring programs for pesticide residues in food – Results from 2001 to 2010’, *Food Control*, 25(2), pp. 607–616. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2011.11.001>.

Jensen, B.H., Petersen, A. and Christensen, T. (2009) ‘Probabilistic assessment of the cumulative dietary acute exposure of the population of Denmark to organophosphorus and carbamate pesticides’, *Food Additives & Contaminants: Part A*, 26(7), pp. 1038–1048. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02652030902859754>.

Kandyliis, P. (2021) 'Grapes and Their Derivatives in Functional Foods', *Foods*, 10(3), p. 672. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10030672>.

Kazar Soydan, D. *et al.* (2021) 'Evaluation of pesticide residues in fruits and vegetables from the Aegean region of Turkey and assessment of risk to consumers', *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(22), pp. 27511–27519. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-12580-y>.

Keikotlhaile, B.M. and Spanoghe, P. (2010) 'Pesticide Residues in Fruits and Vegetables, Pesticides Formulations, Effects, Fate, Ghent University Belgium', pp. 243–252.

Khan, I.A.T., Parveen, Z. and Ahmed, M. (2007) 'Multi-residue Determination of Organophosphorus Pesticides and Synthetic Pyrethroids in Wheat', 9(6), p. 4. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00128-007-9266-8>.

Kostik, V. (2014) 'Determination of Pesticide Residues in Plant-Based Foods from the Republic of Macedonia', *Journal of Food and Nutrition Sciences*, 2(4), p. 124. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.jfns.20140204.15>.

Kuršvietienė, L. *et al.* (2016) 'Multiplicity of effects and health benefits of resveratrol', *Medicina*, 52(3), pp. 148–155. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.medic.2016.03.003>.

Latif, Y. (2011) 'Assessment of pesticide residues in commonly used vegetables in Hyderabad, Pakistan', *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, p. 5. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2011.07.030>.

Łozowicka, B. *et al.* (2013) 'Evaluation of pesticide residues in fruit from Poland and health risk assessment', *Agricultural Sciences*, p. 6. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4236/as.2013.45B020>.

Łozowicka, B. (2015) 'Health risk for children and adults consuming apples with pesticide residue', *Science of the Total Environment*, (502), pp. 184–198. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.09.026>.

McGovern, P.E., Fleming, S.J. and Katz, S.H. (2005) *The origins and ancient history of wine*. Amsterdam: Gordon and Breach Publishers.

Ministry of Agriculture (MoA) (2022) *Lebanese ministry of agriculture, list of banned pesticides and growth regulators 18-6-2020 (2020)*. Lebanon. Available at: <http://www.agriculture.gov.lb/getattachment/Subjects/Plant-Resources/Plant-Pharmacy/Banned-Pesticides/List-of-banned-pesticides-and-growth-regulators-18-6-2020.pdf?lang=ar-LB>.

Mohasseb, R. *et al.* (2020) 'Survey study on the state of viticulture and wine production in Lebanon', p. 9. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17660/ActaHortic.2020.1276.3>.

Nasreddine, L. *et al.* (2016) 'Dietary exposure to pesticide residues from foods of plant origin and drinks in Lebanon', *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 188(8), p. 485. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-016-5505-y>.

Nougadère, A. *et al.* (2020) 'Dietary exposure to pesticide residues and associated health risks in infants and young children – Results of the French infant total diet study', *Environment International*, 137, p. 105529. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.105529>.

Pezzuto, J.M. (2008) 'Grapes and Human Health: A Perspective', *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 56(16), pp. 6777–6784. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf800898p>.

Pimentel, D. (2005) "'Environmental and Economic Costs of the Application of Pesticides Primarily in the United States'", *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 7(2), pp. 229–252. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-005-7314-2>.

PPDB (2022) *Pesticides Properties DataBase—University of Hertfordshire UK (2020)*. Available at: <http://sitem.herts.ac.uk/aeru/ppdb/en/index.htm> (Accessed: 14 May 2022).

Rahbar, A.R., Mahmoudabadi, M.M.S. and Islam, Md.S. (2015) 'Comparative effects of red and white grapes on oxidative markers and lipidemic parameters in adult hypercholesterolemic humans', *Food & Function*, 6(6), pp. 1992–1998. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5FO00100E>.

Rahhal, N. (2018) *Of reds, whites, and rosé - Executive Magazine*. Available at: <https://www.executive-magazine.com/industry-agriculture/of-reds-whites-and-rose> (Accessed: 2 May 2022).

Ripley, B.D. *et al.* (2000) 'Pesticide Residues on Fruits and Vegetables from Ontario, Canada, 1991–1995', *Journal of AOAC INTERNATIONAL*, 83(1), pp. 196–213. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jaoac/83.1.196>.

Singh, C.K. *et al.* (2016) 'Combination chemoprevention with grape antioxidants', *Molecular Nutrition & Food Research*, 60(6), pp. 1406–1415. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/mnfr.201500945>.

Sudaryanto, A. *et al.* (2007) 'Levels and distribution of organochlorines in fish from Indonesia', *Environment International*, 33(6), pp. 750–758. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2007.02.009>.

Szpyrka, E. (2015) 'Evaluation of pesticide residues in fruits and vegetables from the region of south-eastern Poland', *Food Control*, (48), pp. 137–142. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2014.05.039>.

USEPA (2018) *Cumulative Assessment of Risk from Pesticides*. Available at: <https://www.epa.gov/pesticide-science-and-assessing-pesticide-risks/cumulative-assessment-risk-pesticides> (Accessed: 22 November 2022).

US-EPA Regulations (2022). Available at: <https://www.epa.gov/laws-regulations/regulations> (Accessed: 2 May 2022).

WHO (2022) *The WHO Recommended Classification of Pesticides by Hazard and guidelines to classification, 2019 edition*. Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240005662> (Accessed: 8 May 2022).

WHO/GEMS/FOOD and Programme and G.E.M.S.F.C. (2006) *Food regional diets : regional per capita consumption of raw and semi-processed agricultural commodities/prepared by the Global Environment Monitoring System (GEMS/Food) /Food Contamination Monitoring and Assessment Program*. Rev. ed. Available at: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/63989>.

WHO/GEMS/FOOD and Programme, G.E.M.S.F.C. and M. (2006) 'Food regional diets : regional per capita consumption of raw and semi- processed agricultural commodities/prepared by the Global Environment Monitoring System (GEMS/Food) /Food Contamination Monitoring and Assessment Program.' Available at: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/63989> (Accessed: 15 May 2022).

Xiao, O. *et al.* (2020) 'Influence of Triazole Pesticides on Wine Flavor and Quality Based on Multidimensional Analysis Technology', *Molecules*, 25(23), p. 5596. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25235596>.

Zhixia, L., Nie, J. and Yan, Z. (2018) 'A monitoring survey and dietary risk assessment for pesticide residues on T peaches in China', (97), pp. 152–162. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2018.06.007>.